

EFFECTS OF GINGER AND BLACK PEPPER SEED EXTRACTS ON THE NUTRITIONAL QUALITY OF OVEN-DRIED *CLARIAS GARIEPINUS*

¹Ugo P. C., ¹Adaka G. S., ¹Anyanwu C. N., ¹Utah, C. and ²Onyeonula N. I

¹*Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture Technology, Federal University of Technology PMB.1526,
Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria*

²*Biology Department, Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri*

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Abstract: *The nutritional quality of oven dried Clarias gariiepinus pretreated with ginger and black pepper extract and stored in ambient temperature for a period of 21 days was assessed using proximate, microbial composition and organoleptic evaluation. Two hundred and ten (210) freshly caught Clarias gariiepinus weighing 500g were killed, gutted, washed thoroughly with portable water and brimmed by dipping in 15% sodium chloride solution for 3minutes. They were drained and divided into 7 segments of 10 fish each in triplicates. The spices (ginger and black pepper extract) were grounded and diluted with water respectively and applied as oml for control, 10ml, 20ml and 30ml respectively for both the ginger and the black pepper. The fish were oven dried for five hours, cooled, packaged in bulk and stored in ambient temperature of 25°C for 21 days. The samples were subjected to organoleptic, proximate, microbial and biochemical analysis. Result of the proximate composition showed a significant difference among the samples. In the crude protein, 30% black pepper had the highest value of 69.92 followed by 20% black pepper with a value of 69.77 and then the 20% ginger with the value of 68.58 respectively while the control had the least value of 67.68. The moisture ranges from control 6.75 to the lowest value of 30% black pepper with a value of 6.47. The highest crude fat was recorded in 30% black pepper (8.41) followed by 20% black pepper with the value of 8.33. However, there were no significant difference among the 20% and 30% black pepper value ($p < 0.05$). The control showed the least values for both the crude protein and the fat content. The organoleptic assessment studies showed differences within samples in respect to the appearance, flavour, texture and colours of the fish. General taste preference was given to black pepper at 30%. The microbial evaluation showed the control differed significantly within the spices of black pepper and the ginger ($p < 0.05$). The values got from the control were high in total plate count, total coliforms, E. coli, pathogenic microorganisms such as (salmonella) and staphylococcus when compared to the ginger and black pepper. The treatments with spices had a positive effect on the nutritional quality of the products.*

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Introduction

Fish constitutes a very important component of diet for many people and often provides much needed nutrients for a healthy living. Fish serves as a principal source of dietary protein, which is less expensive in relation to other protein foods (Fawole *et al.*, 2007). It is the characteristics of fish as a source of animal protein, which is now evident throughout the world that makes it an excellent component of human diet. Fish protein now takes precedence over other protein of animal origin and compares favorably with that of milk, egg, and meat in its amino acid composition. It is this quality that makes fish protein to be practically indispensable to developing countries, such as Nigeria, for diet supplementation where the staple diet or food consist primarily of starchy foods (Idris *et al.*, 2010). Fish is also known to possess a very high amount of fats and oil and fish fat is very high in polyunsaturated fatty acids, which are very important in lowering blood cholesterol level. The oil on the other hand, contains the fat-soluble vitamins. Fish is also a very good source of thiamine, riboflavin, contains minerals, phosphatides sterols, enzymes hormones, hydrocarbons and pigments (Larsen *et al.*, 2007) (Usydu, 2009). However, fish deteriorate very fast if not well preserved. The spoilage of fish is caused by lipid oxidation and microbial proliferation. Lipid oxidation causes reduction in nutritional quality of fish. It also imparts offensive odour on the fish which affects its consumption and ultimately its marketability (Sallam *et al.*, 2004). Microbial contamination

can be dangerous to the health of humans as was reported in Europe (contamination of fruits by *E. coli* in Europe especially, Germany). Apart from nutritional loss, the presence of micro-organisms in fish can result in massive economic loss. This is very common in developing countries with inadequate and inefficient storage facilities. (Kumolu-Johnson and Ndimele, 2011).

Some processing methods have been used over the years to extend the shelf life of fish in Nigeria and other parts of the world; Curing, chilling, freezing, salting, drying, canning and smoking. (Kumolu-Johnson and Ndimele, 2011). These processing methods have their advantages and disadvantages which dictate their usage in particular parts of the world. Fish smoking is one of the traditional methods of preservation of fish in Africa. In spite of the relative success of fish smoking especially in terms of increasing the shelf life and nutritional quality of fish, the volume of post-harvest losses particularly in sub-Saharan Africa is quite much. Although popular, fish smoking suffers some inherent problems, including un-even cooking of the product, scorching and burning due to direct heating, bitterness, unattractive appearance, rancidity development, limited shelf life and insect infestation (Kumolu-Johnson and Ndimele, 2011). The use of traditional fish smoking oven and direct use of firewood is laborious, resulting in low quality fish of low market value. Attempts have been made to develop improved ovens for fish smoking in Africa. The limitation of this has been the high

cost involved, operational inconveniences and low level of dryness. Rancidity development may also affect the nutritional value, keeping quality as well as consumer acceptance of the fish product. Idris *et al.*, (2010) reported fungal spoilage, lipid oxidation with attendant production of off flavours and poor storage stability of smoke-dried fish as some of the problems of the fish industry in Nigeria.

Synthetic anti-oxidants like butylatedhydroxytoluene (BHT) and Butylatedhydroxyansole (BHA) have been very effective in controlling rancidity (Martinez-Tome *et al.*, 2001). However, these synthetic anti-oxidants have been withdrawn from the market because of their undesirable effects on the enzyme of the liver and lung of humans. This has necessitated the use of natural non antioxidants, such as spices in the preservation of rancidity in smoked fish. Spices are edible plant materials (leaf in onion and garlic, rhizome in ginger) that have anti-oxidative, antiseptic and bacterio-static properties. They are added to foods such as fish, meat to delay the onset of rancidity and reduce microbial proliferation (Eyo, 2001). They also function as seasonings and as well impart flavor to the foods. Ginger is enjoying wider usage in the local food industries as it is added to local delicacies to improve their flavor, shelf life and consumer acceptability (Osuntogun and Aboaba, 2009). Ginger as a spice has a geographical spread that covers every part of the globe and it is consumed whole as a delicacy, used in traditional oriental medicine, or as spice in foods, such as fish (Onyeagba *et al.*, 2004). Black pepper seed is a popular local spice mainly used in Nigerian

dishes. It gives this hot slightly bitter aroma to the food. The spice is known to provide nutritional, culinary, insecticidal and medicinal benefits. It contains proteins, carbohydrates, alkaloids, steroids, glycosides, saponins, flavonoids, tannins and phenolic compounds, also vitamins, minerals and fat (Becky and Onoise, 2017).

Materials and Methods

Fresh ginger and black pepper seed were processed by scrapping off the outer coverings washed, weighed, grind with kitchen blender (Kenwood 5000 W) and 500 gm of each spice was diluted with 5 liters of water respectively boiled for 5minutes, allowed to cool, filtered and applied as ginger and black pepper spice respectively to the three batches of fish at 0ml as control, 10ml, 20ml and 30ml respectively allowed for 10minutes. Two hundred and ten freshly caught *Clarias gariepinus* weighing 500 g were killed, gutted and washed thoroughly with portable water and brimmed by dipping in 15% sodium chloride solution for 3 minutes, drained and divided into 7 segments of 10 fish each. Each treatment was in triplicates of 10 fish in a completely randomized design. Then the prepared spices were applied as ginger and black pepper spice respectively to the three batches of fish at 0ml as control, 10ml, 20ml and 30ml respectively allowed for 10 minutes. The fish was oven dried for seven hours; using charcoal at the temperature of 60-70°C and the dried fish was cooled, packaged in bulk and stored in ambient temperature of 25°C for 21 days. The fish muscle was subjected to proximate, microbial and organoleptic analysis.

Proximate Analysis

The determination of crude protein, moisture, ash and fat content of the fish muscle was carried out using standard methods (AOAC, 1995). Total free fatty acid (FFA) was determined by the method of (Barassi *et al.*, 1987). Samples were analyzed chemically according to the official methods of analysis described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (A.O.A.C, 2005). All analysis carried out in triplicate.

The crude protein in the sample were determined by the routine semi-micro Kjeldahl, procedure/technique. This consists of three phases of analysis namely Digestion, Distillation and Titration using analytical Balance, digestion tubes, Digestion Block Heaters, 50 ml Burette, 5 ml Pipette, 10 ml Measuring cylinder, 100 ml Beakers, Fume Cupboard. Reagents used were Conc H₂SO₄, 0.01NHCL, 40% Boric Acid Solution, Methyl Red Bromocresol green mixed indicator, Kjeldahl Catalyst tablet. Each of the finely grind dried sample of 0.5g was weighed carefully into the Kjeldahl catalyst tablet and 10 ml of Conc H₂SO₄. These were set in the appropriate hole of the Digestion Block Heaters in a fume cupboard. The digestion was left on for 4 hours, after which a clear colorless solution was left in the tube. The digestion was cooled and carefully transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask, thoroughly rinsing the digestion tube with distilled water and the flask was made up to mark with distilled water.

The distillation was done with Markham Distillation Apparatus which allows volatile substances such as ammonia to be steam distilled with complete collection of the distillate. The apparatus was steamed out for

about ten minutes. The steam generator is then removed from the heat source to the entire developing vacuum to remove condensed water. The steam generator is then placed on the heat source (i.e. heating mantle) and each component of the apparatus was fixed up appropriately.

The mixture was steam-distilled for 2 minutes into a 50 ml conical flask containing 10 ml of 2% Boric Acid plus mixed indicator solution placed at the receiving tip of the condenser. The Boric Acid plus indicator solution changes color from red to green showing that all the ammonia liberated have been trapped. The green color obtained was then titrated against 0.01NHCL contained in a 50 ml Burette. At the end point or equivalent point, the green color turns to wine color which indicates that all the Nitrogen trapped as Ammonium Borate (NH₄)₂BO₃ have been removed as Ammonium chloride (NH₄CL).

Determination of Crude Fat or Ether Extract

One gram of each of dried sample was weighed into fat free extraction thimble and pug lightly with cotton wool. The thimble was placed in the extractor and fitted up with reflux condenser and a 250ml Soxhlet flask which has been previously dried in the oven, cooled in the desiccator and weighed. The Soxhlet flask is then filled to $\frac{3}{4}$ of its volume with petroleum ether (b.pt. -60 °C), and the Soxhlet flask. Extractor plus condenser set was placed on the heater. The heater was put on for six hours with constant running water from the tap for condensation of ether vapor. The set is constantly watched for ether leaks and the heat source is adjusted appropriately for the ether to

boil gently. The ether is left to siphon over several times at least 10-12 times until it stop siphoning. It is after this is noticed that any ether content of the extractor is carefully drained into the ether stock bottle. The thimble containing sample is then removed and dried on a clock glass on the bench top. The extractor, flask and condenser were replaced and the distillation continues until the flask is practically dry. The flask which now contains the fat or oil is detached, it's exterior cleaned and dried to a constant weight in the oven. If the initial weight of dry Soxhlet flask is W_0 and the final weight of oven dried flask + oil/fat is obtained by the formula: $\frac{W_1 - W_0}{\text{Wt of Sample taken}} \times 100$

Determination Dry Matter and Moisture Content

About 2gm of the sample was weighed into a previously weighed crucible. The crucible plus sample was then transferred into the oven set at 100°C to dry to a constant weight for 24hrs overnight. At the end of 24hrs, the crucible plus sample was removed from the oven and then transferred to the desiccator, cooled for ten minutes and weighed.

If the weight of empty crucible is W_0

Weight of crucible plus sample is W_1

Weight of crucible plus oven dried sample W_3

$$(\%DM) \%Dr Matter = \frac{W_3 - W_0}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100$$

$$\% Moisture = \frac{W_1 - W_3}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100$$

Or % Moisture = % DM.

Determination of Ash

The sample were weighed in 2.0 gm into a porcelain crucible. This was transferred into the muffle furnace set at 55 °C and left for about 4

hours. About this time, it had turned to white ash. The crucible and its content were cooled to about 100° C in the air, then room temperature in a desiccator and weighed. This was done in duplicate. The percentage ash was calculated from the formula below:

$$\text{Ash content} = \frac{\text{Wt of ash}}{\text{Original wt of Sample}} \times 100$$

Fiber Determination (AOAC 958.06)

Two grams of the sample was accurately weighed into the fiber flask and 100ml of 0.255NH₂SO₄ added. The mixture was heated under the reflux for 1 hour with the heating mantle. The hot mixture was filtered through a sieve cloth. The filtrate obtained was thrown off and the residue was returned to the fiber flask to which 100ml of (0.313N NaOH) was added and heated under reflux for another 1 hour. The mixture was filtered through a fiber sieve cloth and 10ml of acetone added to dissolve any organic constituent. The residue was washed with about 50ml hot water on the sieve cloth before it was finally transferred into the crucible. The crucible and the residue were oven dried at 105°C overnight to drive off moisture. The oven dried crucible containing the residue was cooled in a desiccator and later weighed to obtain the weight W_1 . The crucible with weight W_1 was transferred to the muffle furnace for ash at 550C for 4 hours. The crucible containing white or grey ash (free of carbonaceous material) was cooled in the desiccator and weighed to obtain W_2 . The difference $W_1 - W_2$ gives the weight of fiber. The percentage fiber was obtained by the formula:

$$\% Fiber = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{\text{Wt of Sample}} \times 100$$

Microbial Analysis

One gram representatives' sample was obtained aseptically from the muscle of each of the dried samples. The samples were grinded, and fourfold serial dilutions (10⁻¹-10⁻⁴) of the homogenized samples were made using sterile distilled water. Each analysis was carried out in triplicates. The fish samples were analyzed for total plate count, total coliforms, *E. coli*, and pathogenic microorganisms (salmonella). All microbial analysis were done following the methods prescribed by AOAC (2000). The results were reported in colony-forming units per gram (cfu/g). Aliquots of the suitable dilutions were transferred separately to plates count agar for total plate count, Salmonella, MacConke agar selective media for total colrouts count. Morphological characteristics were used to identify the different bacteria in the agar during plate count. As Salmonella does not ferment lactose but produce hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) gas, the colonies observed were colorless with black center

Organoleptic Evaluation

The room chosen for assessment was designed in such a way as to ensure maximum privacy and to reduce distraction from passerby. A panel of 10 persons was selected on their knowledge of the product to be tested. A form that contained instructions (guide) was issued to each panelist so that every evaluation was carried out bias free. During the taste evaluation, every individual panelist rinsed his or her mouth properly with clean water after each sample of the oven dried fish was evaluated for taste response by eating the fish samples and noting the result. Evaluation was also carried out for texture and color, using hand to ascertain its

muscular relationship to the skin if is firm, feeble or soft and sense of sight to ascertain if the colour is dull or attractive to the eyes.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1, shows results of crude protein: the group of fish treated with black pepper had the highest value. Black pepper at 30 ml had 69.92, at 20 ml (69.77), at 10 ml 69.52 followed by the group with ginger spice, 20 ml had 68.58 ginger 30 ml (68.38), 10 ml (68.22) and the control 67.68. The Crude fat revealed the group of fish treated with black pepper, had the highest value. Black pepper at 30 ml had 8.41, 20 ml (8.33%), 10 ml (7.95) followed by ginger 30 ml, (8.23), 20 ml (0.82), 10 ml (0.64) and the lowest value of 7.66 in the control. Crude fiber: groups treated with ginger had the highest value followed by the groups with black pepper spice while the control was 0. ginger 30 ml is 0.93, ginger 20 ml (0.82), ginger 10 ml (0.64), 30 ml black pepper (0.55), 20 ml black pepper (0.48), 10 ml black pepper (0.42) and control (0). Ash: groups treated with black pepper had the highest value followed by the groups with ginger spice while the control had the lowest value. 30 ml black pepper is 9.64, 20 ml black pepper (9.58), 10 ml black pepper (9.45), ginger 30 ml (9.34), ginger 20 ml (9.21), ginger 10 ml (8.92) and the control 8.38. Moisture: groups treated with ginger at 30 ml and 10 ml had the highest value followed by ginger at 20 ml and the control while the groups treated with black pepper had the least value. Ginger 30 ml (6.91), ginger10 ml (6.80), control (6.75), ginger 20 ml (6.67), 10 ml black pepper (6.59), 20 ml black pepper (6.52) and 30 ml black pepper (6.47).

Nitrogen Fat Extract: The control had the highest value followed by the groups treated with ginger spice while the groups treated with black pepper had the least value. Control ,9.52, ginger 10 ml (7.45), ginger 20 ml (6.65), ginger 30 ml (6.20),10 ml black pepper (5.93), 20 ml black pepper (5.31) and 30 ml black pepper (5.00)

Dry Matter: groups treated with black pepper had the highest value followed by the groups with ginger spice. Black pepper at 30 ml is 93.53, 20 ml black pepper (93.47), 10 ml black pepper (93.41), 20 ml ginger (93.32), control (93.25), 10 ml ginger (93.19), and 30 ml ginger (93.08).

Table 1: Proximate composition of Oven Dried Fish.

	Control	Ginger			Black pepper		
		10ml	20ml	30ml	10ml	20ml	30ml
Crude Protein	67.68 ^e	68.22 ^d	68.58 ^c	68.38 ^{cd}	69.52 ^b	69.77 ^a	69.92 ^a
Crude Fat	7.66 ^e	7.95 ^d	8.07 ^c	8.23 ^b	8.08 ^c	8.33 ^a	8.41 ^a
Crude Fibre	0 ^f	0.64 ^c	0.82 ^b	0.93 ^a	0.42 ^e	0.48 ^{de}	0.55 ^d
Ash	8.38 ^f	8.92 ^e	9.21 ^d	9.34 ^c	9.45 ^b	9.58 ^a	9.64 ^a
Moisture	6.75 ^b	6.80 ^{ab}	6.67 ^{bc}	6.91 ^a	6.59 ^{cd}	6.52 ^d	6.47 ^d
NFE	9.52 ^a	7.45 ^b	6.65 ^c	6.20 ^d	5.93 ^e	5.31 ^f	5.00 ^g
DM	93.25 ^d	93.19 ^c	93.32 ^c	93.08 ^{bc}	93.41 ^{ab}	93.47 ^a	93.53 ^a

Values with superscript letter on the same row are significantly difference ($p \geq 0.05$)

In Table 2, Total plate count: the highest value was seen in the control followed by the group treated with ginger 30 ml, 10 ml and 20 ml while the groups with black pepper had the lowest value. Control 3.53, 30 ml ginger (3.09), 10 ml ginger (2.94), 20 ml ginger (2.79), 10 ml black pepper (2.33), 20 ml pepper (2.08), 30 ml black pepper (1.88). Total Coliform count: the highest value was recorded in the control followed by the group treated with ginger at 30 ml, 10 ml and 20 ml while the groups with black pepper had the lowest value. Control 4.19, 30 ml ginger (4.12), 20 ml ginger (3.94), 10 ml ginger (3.85), 10 ml black pepper (3.56), 20 ml black pepper (3.31) and 30 ml black pepper (3.17). E. Coli: the highest value was recorded in the control

followed by the group treated with ginger 30 ml,10 ml and 20 ml while the groups with black pepper had the lowest value the value ranges from control 6.64, 30 ml ginger (6.37), 10 ml ginger (5.84), 10 ml black pepper (5.49), 20 ml black pepper (5.26), and 30 ml black pepper (5.08). Staphylococcus: the highest value was recorded in the control followed by the group treated with ginger at 30 ml, 10 ml and 20 ml while the groups with black pepper had the lowest value. Control. 4.76, 30 ml ginger (4.58), 10 ml ginger (4.41), 20 ml ginger (3.79), 10 ml black pepper (3.45), 20 ml black pepper (3.17), 30 ml black pepper (3.11). Salmonella the highest value was recorded in the control followed by the group treated with ginger at 30 ml, 10 ml and 20 ml while the groups with black pepper had the lowest value. Control 2.51, 30 ml

ginger (2.38), 10 ml ginger (2.17), 20 ml ginger (2.04), 10 ml black pepper (1.99), 20 ml black pepper (1.92) and 30 ml black pepper (1.82).

Table 2: Microbial Analysis of Oven Dried Fish

	Control	Ginger			Black pepper			SEM
		10ml	20ml	30ml	10ml	20ml	30ml	
TPC (cfu/g)	3.53 ^a	2.94 ^c	2.79 ^d	3.09 ^b	2.33 ^e	2.08 ^f	1.88 ^g	0.12
TCC (cfu/g)	4.19 ^a	3.94 ^c	3.85 ^d	4.12 ^b	3.56 ^e	3.31 ^f	3.17 ^g	0.08
E. coli(cfu/g)	6.64 ^a	5.84 ^c	5.69 ^d	6.37 ^b	5.49 ^e	5.26 ^f	5.08 ^g	0.11
Staphylococcus (cfu/g)	4.76 ^a	4.41 ^c	3.79 ^d	4.58 ^b	3.45 ^e	3.17 ^f	3.11 ^f	0.14
Salmonella (cfu/g)	2.51 ^a	2.17 ^c	2.04 ^{ds}	2.38 ^b	1.99 ^{ef}	1.92 ^f	1.82 ^g	0.05

Values with superscript letter on the same row are significantly difference ($p \geq 0.05$)

In the table 3 below treatments with black pepper had the highest score for taste compared to other treatments. Black pepper at 30% had the highest preference. **Flavor:** The treatments with black pepper and ginger had the highest

preference than the control. Black pepper at 30% had the highest preference.

Texture: treatments with black pepper and ginger had the highest preference in terms of texture more than the control. **Colour:** treatments with ginger and black pepper had the highest preference compared to the control. Ginger at 30% had the highest preference.

Table 3: Organoleptic Assessment of Oven Dried Fish

Ginger					
Variables	0	10ml	20ml	30ml	SEM
Taste	45 ^d	49 ^c	70 ^b	75 ^a	3.91
Flavor	52 ^d	54 ^c	56 ^b	65 ^a	1.51
Texture	47 ^b	47 ^b	51 ^a	47 ^b	0.57
Color	49 ^b	49 ^b	50 ^b	66 ^a	2.19
Black Pepper					
Variables	0	10ml	20ml	30ml	SEM
Taste	45 ^c	74 ^b	74 ^b	85 ^a	4.48
Flavor	52 ^d	65 ^b	62 ^c	70 ^a	2.11
Texture	47 ^c	56 ^b	58 ^a	59 ^a	1.45
Colour	49 ^d	56 ^c	59 ^b	64 ^a	1.65

Research on catfish shows that spice pretreatments (mainly ginger, garlic, turmeric, clove, other herbs, and black pepper) can improve nutritional quality, reduce microbial spoilage, and enhance consumer acceptability of smoked/dried *Clarias gariepinus* (Ekelemu, *et al.*, 2021, Kefas, *et al.* 2023 and Ojukannaiye, *et al.*,2020). The data from this research fit well within this pattern, with black pepper generally superior for protein, fat, dry matter and microbial control, and ginger contributing more fiber, moisture and some sensory benefits. There is a probability that ginger at 30 ml absorbed more water than the other treatments however, the values are in line with the specified 10% ISO standard in food material. Fish can easily spoil when the moisture content is above 10%. This also agrees with the findings of Kumolu (2001), and Utah, *et. al* (2021) which stated that the use of salt and garlic respectively together with either sun drying or smoking could significantly reduce moisture as well as the spoilage of fish from the action of enzymes and bacteria.

The percentage crude protein content ranged between 67.68 in the control, 68.58 in 20 ml gingers to 69.92 in 30 ml black pepper. The increase in the value of fish treated with ginger and black pepper could be as result of the active materials contained by the spices that enhanced the crude protein content. The protein level reported in this study agrees with the values recorded by Magawata, and Shina (2013) and Agbabiaka *et al.*, (2016) on processed African catfish.

The Crude Fat values ranged between 7.66 in control, 8.23 in 30 ml ginger and 8.41 in 30 ml

in black pepper. The increase in the value within the treatments with spices could be as a result of the nutrient concentration in the spices. The increase in the crude protein of the treatments with black pepper is in agreement with the study done by Morufu *et al.* (2016), Ibrahim and Adaka (2022) which stated that black pepper improved the fat content of the fish due to its high crude fat levels.

Crude Fiber: The fiber content ranged between 0 in the control, 0.55 in 30 ml black pepper and 30 ml ginger 0.93. The highest value got in ginger is because of the high fiber content of the ginger.

The result shows that the mean value of the microbial parameters tested for, in the *Clarias gariepinus* after storage in ambient room temperature for 21 days, revealed that control had the highest value followed by ginger and the black pepper having the lowest values respectively. A broader fish-spice study notes that *Piper guineense* (West African black pepper) significantly reduced microbial loads on smoked catfish and *Synodontis* over months of storage, confirming strong preservative power in fish systems (Agbabiaka, *et. al.*, 2016).

There is significant difference within the samples of the fish treated with the spices. The microbial results observed in this study are in agreement with the studies of Kumolu-Johnson and Ndimele (2011) in which it was observed that there was a reduction in microbial proliferation and lipid oxidation in the samples treated with ginger paste. This also support the work done by Anyanwu and Nwosu (2014) where the leaf extract of black pepper inhibited the growth of all the microbial isolates tested.

The reduction in the values of black pepper supports the study by Morufu *et al.* (2016) which stated that black pepper has phytochemicals present in it which are rich in flavonoids, tannins, saponins and alkaloids which have been found to have antimicrobial properties.

In the free fatty acids profile, samples with ginger and black pepper showed higher Free Fatty Acid profile values than the control. This shows that ginger and black pepper had positive effect on the fish. Results shows that the various concentrations of ginger and black pepper used in this experiment increased FFA production. This is contrary with the study conducted by Idris *et al.*, 2011 where the control showed higher free fatty acid when compared with the treatments with ginger at different concentration. The free fatty acid content in a product is an indication of the quality of the product (Clucas and Ward, 1996).

The appearance of the control was the least preferred by the panelist. Ginger and black pepper recorded better sensory score. The taste of the black pepper at 30 ml was highly preferred than the others. The highest rate in terms of taste and aroma was black pepper. This could be attributed to some phenolic and carbonyl compound present in the spice. Some phenolic compounds are the guaiacol and cypringol

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which are characteristically seen in smoked fish (Anyanwu *et al.*, 2016), it is assumed that the reactions between the carbonyl compounds and proteins are responsible for color formation on smoked fish surfaces while the absorbed phenolic compounds are for flavor and aroma for smoked fish. Luten *et al.*, (1986).

Aroma is reported to be perceived as volatile odors diffusing from the food which are taken up by the nose and detected by the olfactory receptors there in (Yusuf, *et al.*, 2025). From the result the best oven dried fish sample with respect to general acceptability was black pepper at 30 ml followed by ginger at 30 ml.

Conclusion

The study showed that the application of ginger and black pepper to fish before oven drying improved the nutrients of fish and also inhibited the growths of microbes. From the results, it appeared that black pepper as spice has shown to have a good potential as microbial agent. Black pepper at 30 ml appeared to be more efficient and effective concentration without deleterious effect on the nutrient. It is therefore recommended to pretreat fish with these spices before oven drying to improve and preserve nutrients in them for increased shelf life and consumer's acceptability.

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